

Research

Difficulties Encountered by School Administrators in Handling Financial Matters at Secondary Schools within the Lahore District

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Abstract: This research aimed to identify the difficulties faced by school administrators in managing finances at secondary schools in Lahore District, Punjab Pakistan. The study included all 30 secondary schools in the district as its population, and a sample of ten schools was chosen randomly. From those schools, 40 respondents were selected purposefully. The research employed a descriptive survey design and collected data through questionnaires and interviews. The findings revealed that many school heads lacked the necessary accounting skills to effectively manage school finances. Additionally, there was little or no supervision from the Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education finance department personnel on financial management matters. The study recommends the implementation of capacity building programs for school heads, deputy heads, and members of the school development committees. Moreover, the Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education should increase both announced and unannounced school visits to monitor financial usage.

Keywords: Challenges, schools heads, secondary school, school finances, management, district.

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Introduction

In Punjab province of Pakistan, the management of school finances is governed by Provincial Ministry of Education which is linked with federal government finance and education ministry which stipulates the role of key players in the school set-up and the involvement of parents through the school development committees for non-governmental schools and school development associations for government schools (Mehmood, 2004). Management of finances is therefore, one of the key duties of a school head and they are expected to work with the school development committees/associations. According to a research (Carter, J. R. and Narasimhan, R. (2006), the management of finances in many rural schools has been poor and this has significantly affected the quality of education provided by these schools. The number of cases of embezzlement of funds by school heads and misappropriation are quite frightening (Barbie, E. 2008). This means that schools in rural areas are deprived of their meager resources due to embezzlement,

misappropriation, and fraud (Carter, J. R. and Narasimhan, R. (2006). According to Statutory Instrument 1 of 2000, a head who fails to account for school funds faces discharge from service and imminent arrest. As Cohen, L. and Manion, L. (2005) posits, although some criminal elements amongst the heads are responsible for the misuse of school funds, in the majority of cases, heads fail to account for finances due to a lack of financial background and expertise on financial matters. It is within this context that the study sought to investigate the challenges that school heads experience in the process of managing school funds (Mehmood, 2004 & Chivore, B. R.S, 1995).

Literature review

Financial management has proven to be a persistent challenge in many schools as a result of inadequate training of school managers Davies, B. (2009). Mestry (2004) reports that many school principals and members of school governing boards lack the financial expertise and skills required to effectively manage school finances. Consequently, they face enormous pressure as they struggle to find practical solutions to financial problems. In some instances, school principals and members of governing boards have been subjected to forensic audits due to their mismanagement of funds. Misappropriation, fraud, pilfering of cash, theft, and inadequate control of school funds are some of the common issues leading to financial mismanagement (Mestry, 2004).

The heads of schools or principals are responsible for managing all financial activities involving the collection and distribution of funds. Orlosky (2004) notes that the head or principal is responsible for budgeting, accounting, and auditing functions in financial management. In Pakistan, the head of schools serves as an ex-officio member of the school development committee, as stated by Chivore (1995). However, according to Karlson (2002), heads or principals still hold a dominant role in decision-making and meetings during school development committee meetings. This is due to their position of power within the school, their level of education, and their access to information from educational authorities before other members, particularly from the parents' side (Van Wyk, 2004).

Mpofu (2005) argues that the role of the head of school is problematic due to its dual nature. On one hand, the head is accountable to the school development committee as an accounting officer, and on the other hand, they are accountable to the education department as an employee. This dual role can lead to controversy and conflict. As Chivore (1995) notes, school heads can potentially undermine decentralized governance structures by retaining control for themselves. However, the role of the head of school in the school development committee is crucial. They are required to liaise with various departments and agencies, similar to a chief executive officer of a company, to ensure the well-being of the school (Mpofu, 2005).

Proper financial management is crucial to the success of a school, and a well-planned and executed budget is essential to achieving financial stability. According to Rehman (2002), school heads and finance committees should base their budget projections on reliable data of expected incomes and expenditures, which serve as guides for financial planning and program management. Effective control of school finances is necessary to ensure that the school's objectives and needs are met, and correct budgetary procedures must be followed to avoid interruptions or restrictions due to insufficient funds or depleted accounts (Jordan et al., 2008; Van der, 1991). The school development committee is responsible for keeping written records of all financial transactions, including money and property of the school (Bisschoff, 2007).

Financial control also involves ensuring that all financial transactions are properly documented and recorded, and that proper accounting procedures are followed (Davies, 2009). As stated by Bisschoff (2007), the school development committee should ensure that accurate financial records are kept, that all transactions are properly authorized, and that there are appropriate checks and balances in place to prevent fraud or mismanagement of funds. Effective financial control can help to prevent financial problems and ensure that the school is able to achieve its goals and objectives (Van Der Berg, 2002).

This ongoing process of monitoring and evaluation is crucial in ensuring that the school's financial management is efficient and effective. As Chivore (1995) notes, a system of regular monitoring and evaluation helps to detect

problems and allows for timely corrective action to be taken. Furthermore, it provides a means of ensuring that resources are being used in line with the school's objectives and priorities. As such, regular monitoring and evaluation of the budget should be a key element of any school's financial management strategy.

The problem at hand is the mismanagement of school finances by school heads, which can negatively impact the quality of education for learners. Despite the importance of proper financial management in schools, many school heads lack the necessary training and skills to effectively manage school finances. This can lead to financial mismanagement, including misappropriation of funds, fraud, and theft, which can have serious consequences for the school and its learners. Additionally, the dual nature of the role played by the school head, being accountable to both the school development committee and the education department, can create conflicts of interest and further complicate financial management. To ensure that school finances are managed effectively and transparently, it is essential to investigate and address the underlying causes of financial mismanagement by school heads.

Research Questions

1. Do schools have functional finance committees?
2. Are school finances audited internally by the school finance committee?
3. Does the finance department in the Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education advise and monitor schools on financial administration?
4. What role does the school development committee play in the administration of finances?
5. What measures need to be put in place to monitor the implementation of finance policies in schools?

Significance of the study

The study's importance is significant as it addresses a critical issue in the education sector that affects the proper functioning of schools and the education of learners. By identifying the challenges faced by school heads in managing school finances, the study provides insights into the current state of financial administration in schools, which can inform policy decisions and interventions. The study's findings can guide the development of effective strategies and solutions that can improve financial management practices in schools, ultimately contributing to better learning outcomes for learners. Additionally, the study's results can assist development partners in directing their resources towards the areas of greatest need, and the communities in holding school heads accountable for the effective management of school finances.

Limitations of the study

It is important to note that while the sample size used in the study may be relatively small, it is not uncommon for qualitative research to employ small sample sizes. The purpose of qualitative research is to gain a deeper understanding of a particular phenomenon rather than making statistical generalizations. Regarding the use of descriptive design, it is true that it lacks predictive power, but it is still a valuable method for exploring a phenomenon in-depth. Additionally, the researcher can use other methods such as case studies, experiments or quasi-experiments if they want to make predictions or causal inferences. The concern about false responses from participants is valid, but this can be mitigated by using multiple data collection methods, cross-checking information provided by participants, and conducting member checks to validate findings.

Delimitations of the study refer to the boundaries and constraints that the researcher imposes on the study. In this case, the study is delimited to the challenges faced by school heads in the management of school finances in Lahore District. The sample size of the study is limited to 40 respondents consisting of heads, deputy heads, senior teachers, and school development committee treasurers. Therefore, the findings of the study cannot be generalized to other districts or regions in Pakistan, and the results are only applicable to the context of Lahore District. Additionally, the study is delimited to the perspectives of the selected respondents and does not include the perspectives of other stakeholders such as students, parents, or other members of the community.

Research Methodology

Quantitative research is a research method that uses numerical data to understand and analyze phenomena. The survey design is a popular method of collecting data in quantitative research. A survey involves asking a set of standardized questions to a group of people to gather data about their attitudes, beliefs, behaviors, and experiences. Purposive sampling is a non-probability sampling technique where the researcher selects participants based on specific criteria related to the research question. This sampling method is used when the researcher wants to study a specific group of individuals who possess unique characteristics or experiences. Random sampling, on the other hand, is a probability sampling technique where each member of the population has an equal chance of being selected for the study. Questionnaires and interviews are common instruments used to collect data in a survey. Questionnaires are self-administered written surveys that are completed by the participants, while interviews involve a researcher asking questions and recording the participant's responses. Both methods allow researchers to gather standardized data from participants and can be used to measure attitudes, opinions, and experiences related to the research question.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Composition of respondents by category (N=40)

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Heads	10	25
Deputy heads	10	25
Senior teachers	10	25
Treasurers	10	25
Totals	40	100

Table 1 shows that there was an equal number of heads (25%), deputy heads (25%), senior teachers (25%) and school development treasurers (25%). This was arrived at using purposive sampling as these categories were seen as the most relevant to provide the information sought for the research.

Table 2: Composition of respondents by sex (N=40).

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	26	66
Female	14	34
Total	40	100

The majority of respondents (66%) were male and females constituted 34% of the sample.

Table 3: Responses to the statement: "The current school development committee is properly constituted" (N=40).

Response category	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	19	47
Not	21	53
Not Sure	0	0
Total	40	100

Table 3 shows that 53% of the respondents indicating that the current School Development Committees at their schools, were illegitimate. Those who said that their School Development Committees were properly constituted were 47% of the respondents.

Table 4: Responses to the statement: “My school has a functional finance committee” (N=40).

Response category	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	10	25
Not	30	75
Not Sure	0	0
Total	40	100

The majority of the respondents (75%) indicated that their schools did not have functioning finance committees. Those who stated that their schools had finance committees that were functioning very well were (25%) of the respondents and these are likely to be the 10 heads of schools.

Table 5: Responses to the question: “When did the officers from the accounts department from Ministry of Education visit your school?”

Response Category	Frequency	Percentage
0 – 2 yrs	0	0
3 – 5 yrs	3	8
6 – 8 yrs	2	5
Never	35	87
Total	40	100

Table 5 reveals that the Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education officers from the accounts department were not visiting schools to monitor and guide the way schools were managing finances.

The researchers conducted interviews with four heads, four deputy heads, four senior teachers and four treasurers from four schools due to proximity to the researchers. The first question from the interview wanted to find out from the respondents whether the school finance committee carried out audits of school accounts. Most of the participants indicated that the finance committee did not exist in their schools. One participant said that “At the beginning of the year, our head promised to create a finance committee, up to now, this is August, it does not exist”. Participants indicated that heads made most decisions on financial matters alone and sometimes invited one member of the school development committee to endorse their decisions.

The participants were also asked about the role of the school development committee in the administration of finances. Most of them stated that the majority of SDC members lacked financial literacy and simply endorsed the decisions of the head. One participant explained that since most SDC members have limited education and availability to spend time at the school, the head is left to make decisions alone under the pressure to act quickly for the school's benefit. It appeared that the SDC's function was only to give the appearance of endorsing the head's plans for the school. Another participant pointed out that SDC members were often friends of the head who had been in their positions for a long time. Some parents were hesitant to challenge them during SDC elections. Some participants noted that when SDC members were well-informed, their relations with the head of school became contentious, as heads felt their professional work was being challenged.

According to the participants, the way forward involves increased involvement of all stakeholders in financial matters concerning the school. They also suggested that heads should receive intensive in-service courses on financial management, particularly for newly promoted heads who may lack experience in financial management. The

participants further implored accounts officers to visit schools frequently to guide heads and SDC members, rather than appearing only when there are cases of financial mismanagement. Some participants expressed frustration with the Ministry's lack of support, noting that funds for workshops and visits are only made available when there are cases of financial mismanagement, rather than being proactively provided to prevent such cases.

The study findings reveal that in Pakistan, the management of school finances is governed by Statutory Instrument 87 of 1992, which stipulates the involvement of school development committees. However, most schools have illegitimate individuals posing as SDC members, according to the study. This finding aligns with Karlson's (2002) observations that heads still dominate meetings and decision-making during SDC meetings, despite the law stating that they should only have an advisory role as ex-officio members. The researchers found that some heads manipulate the SDC election process to surround themselves with friends or individuals who agree with them, leaving other parents powerless to stop the behavior. Van Wyk (2004) attributes this behavior to the head's position of power within the school, their level of education compared to other parents, and their first access to information issued from education authorities. Based on the study's findings, it is clear that more needs to be done to ensure the proper management of school finances in Pakistan.

The issue of the head playing a dominant role also affects the functioning of the school finance committee, as most schools do not have a functional committee. According to Statutory Instrument 87 of 1992, every school is required to establish a finance committee chaired by the head, comprising the head, deputy head, chairperson, and vice-chairperson of the SDC. The committee's mandate is to develop operational budgets for the coming month and review the previous month's expenditures at the beginning of each month. Based on reliable data, the committee makes projections for the coming month, forming the basis for projected expenditures, as described by Rehman (2002). However, it seems that the head carries out all this work in isolation from other committee members. This eliminates the checks and balances that transparent operations allow for when financial matters are openly shared and discussed, as noted by Chikowore (2012). This lack of transparency and accountability contributes to the high number of cases of funds embezzlement by school heads.

The study also found that officers from the accounts department at the Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education were not providing sufficient guidance to heads of schools and school development committees on how to manage school finances. This lack of guidance exacerbates the problem of financial mismanagement in schools. As Mehmood (2004) argues, many heads of schools and members of school development committees are not experts in financial management, and as a result, some heads are dismissed from their positions due to ignorance rather than criminal behavior. Ndlovu (2013) supports this claim, stating that although some criminal elements among school heads are responsible for the misuse of school funds, lack of financial background and expertise is the main reason for many heads' failure to account for funds.

Recommendations

Considering the findings of this study, the researchers recommend that:

- The Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education should periodically monitor the way how heads conduct elections to come up with members of school development committees through proper procedures. All school development committees' elections should be supervised by the Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education district officers.
- There is a need to develop a simple user friendly template that would be easily understood by both heads and members of the school development committees. Schools should also be required to submit monthly or termly financial reports to the district education office so that the district can analyze and give feedback to schools.
- The government and education officers should promote community sensitization and participation on matters of financial management so as to give a sense of school ownership to the community.

Conclusion

Given the background of the above findings, the researchers make the following conclusions:

- Most schools have illegitimate school development committees that exist through the whims and caprices of school heads.
- School heads do not involve school finance committee members in the administration of school finances.
- Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education officers from the accounts department were not providing the necessary guidance to heads and school development committees on legal and operational issues related to finances in schools.

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